

Climateurope2

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan – CDEP

Deliverable 7.1

Authors:

Arianna Acierno - CMCC
Mauro Buonocore - CMCC
Marta Terrado - BSC
Marina Corradini - BSC
Artiza Elozegi - WLT

Internal Reviewers:

Marjana Brkić – CPN
Lale Eric Dobrivoje – CPN

Funded by
the European Union

Climateurope2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101056933.

Document Information

Grant agreement	No 101056933
Project title	Supporting and standardising climate services in Europe and beyond
Project acronym	Climateurope2
Project start date	01/09/2022
Related work package	WP7 Communication, dissemination and exploitation
Related task(s)	T7.1 Communication activities
Lead organisation	CMCC
Authors	Arianna Acierno, Mauro Buonocore
Submission date	28/02/2023
Dissemination level	PU

History

Date	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Vision (notes)
07/02/2023	Arianna Acierno	Marjiana Brkić, Lale Eric Dobrivoje	First draft (v1)
28/02/2023	Arianna Acierno		Final draft (v2)

Please cite this report as: Acierno, A., Buonocore, Terrado M., Corradini M., Elosegi A., Brkić M., Dobrivoje LE., February 2023, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan - CDEP, D7.1 of the Climateurope project.

Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

1	Purpose and objectives of the CDEP	4
2	Key messages	5
3	Target audiences	7
4	Visual identity	8
4.1	Visual identity and logo	8
4.2	Templates	10
4.3	Acknowledgements	12
5	Communication and dissemination tools and channels	13
5.1	Project website	13
5.2	Newsletter	15
5.3	Social media	16
5.4	Climateurope2 Platform	19
5.5	Press releases	20
5.6	Promotional materials	20
5.7	Videos	23
5.8	Podcasts	24
5.9	Infographics	24
5.10	Events	25
5.11	Innovative activities	27
5.12	Clustering activities	28
5.13	Scientific publications	29
5.14	Factsheets	29
5.15	Synthesis reports	30
5.16	Policy briefs	30
5.17	Capacity building	30
6	Monitoring and reporting	33
6.1	Key performance indicators	33
7	Exploitation	35
7.1	Objectives	35
7.2	Methodology	35
7.3	Key exploitable results and overview of usual routes for exploitation in EU projects	37
8	Internal communication	39

List of tables

Table 1. Communication/dissemination tools and target audiences	32
Table 2. KPIs	34

List of figures

Figure 1. Climateurope2 target groups	7
Figure 2. The Climateurope2 logo	8
Figure 3. Examples of the application of the Climateurope2 logo on different backgrounds	9
Figure 4. Climateurope2 visual identity: the colour palette	10
Figure 5. Climateurope2 visual identity: the poster presentation template	11
Figure 6. Climateurope2 visual identity: the presentation template – title slide	12
Figure 7. Climateurope2 website homepage	14
Figure 8. Climateurope2 Twitter account	17
Figure 9. Climateurope2 LinkedIn account	18
Figure 10. Climateurope2 Youtube page (video of the first webinar)	19
Figure 11. Climateurope2 social media planner	19
Figure 12. Climateurope2 flyer	22
Figure 13. Exploitation roadmap and milestones	36
Figure 14. RSB methodology	37
Figure 15. Summary of the main types of exploitable results to emerge from the project	38
Figure 16. Possible routes of exploitation	38
Figure 17. Project actors, types of information available and internal and external communication vectors	39

About Climateurope2

Timely delivery and effective use of climate information is fundamental for a green recovery and a resilient, climate-neutral Europe, in response to climate change and variability. **Climate services address this through the provision of climate information for use in decision-making to manage risks and realise opportunities.**

The market and need for climate information have seen impressive progress in recent years and are expected to grow in the foreseeable future. However, the communities involved in the development and provision of climate services are often unaware of each other and lack interdisciplinary and

transdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, quality assurance, relevant standards, and other forms of assurance (such as guidelines, and good practices) for climate services are lagging behind. These are needed to ensure the saliency, credibility, legitimacy, and authoritativeness of climate services, and build two-way trust between supply and demand.

Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services to all sectors of society by:

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services
- Supporting an equitable European climate services community
- Enhancing the uptake of quality-assured climate services to support adaptation and mitigation to climate change and variability

The project **will identify the support and standardisation needs of climate services, including criteria for certification and labelling, as well as the user-driven criteria needed to support climate action.** This information will be used to propose a taxonomy of climate services, suggest community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. A large variety of activities to support the communities involved in European climate services will also be organised.

Executive Summary

The scope of the Climateurope2 communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (CDEP) is to facilitate the implementation of the project communication activities and make key stakeholders and the general public aware of the project's achievements.

Thus, the CDEP will design and develop certain external communication activities, aimed at creating a network of project-external relationships and making key stakeholders aware of the project's outcomes, while raising awareness of climate services.

The plan illustrates the project objectives in terms of communication, dissemination and exploitation, the main target groups, the main messages to be delivered, the communication and dissemination channels to be used, and the communication activities planned in the framework of the project.

1 Purpose and objectives of the CDEP

Climate change is felt in unprecedented climate extremes, among a large number of other impacts, which have substantive consequences for socio-technical and socio-economic systems. The best science available illustrates that there are more changes to come, with large changes foreseen in regional and local climate. At the same time, addressing the exposure to current climate variability requires the best climate information delivered in a timely fashion, through adequate channels and by appropriate means, especially for regions, populations and economic activities that are most vulnerable to climate change and variability. Climate information has a leading role in achieving a green recovery and climate neutrality in Europe, and the instrumental one for a climate resilient Europe. These roles

can materialise if climate information is delivered appropriately and used effectively, integrating the information with other decision-making elements to better manage risks and realise opportunities. Climate services are created to provide climate information addressing these aspects and supporting decision-making processes to manage risks and seize opportunities.

In this framework, communication, dissemination and exploitation (WP7) play a crucial role in maximising the scientific, economic and societal impact of the project. All project partners contribute to these activities, which have the following objectives:

- enhance the visibility of the objectives and outcomes of the project,
- increase awareness on climate services and promote their uptake,
- build capacity and improve the professional skills of the climate service community,
- ensure the legacy of the project by benefiting the European climate services community beyond the project's lifetime.

WP7 works in close cooperation and coordination with other WPs of the project in the framework of increasing engagement with the climate services community and other stakeholders. For instance, WP7 will leverage activities and materials from WP4 to achieve a more cohesive business community, activities from WP5 will be used to cultivate dialogue with policy makers, and actions of WP6 will be addressed to enhance continuous stakeholder engagement in each phase of the project - to collect inputs from stakeholders in the starting phase and improve the project i.e. outcomes with them in the dissemination phase.

The CDEP lists the target audiences, key messages to be communicated in the project, communication, dissemination and exploitation tools and channels, action plan and social media strategy. All activities will be monitored through KPIs, followed-up and updated to maximise their impact. This will be reflected in impact evaluations and updated versions of the CDEP that will be reported during the project (M18 and M36, corresponding to D7.2 and D7.4). A final evaluation and a communication plan for the project legacy will be provided at the end of the project (M53, D7.6).

2 Key messages

According to the main objectives of ClimateEurope2, four key messages tailored to specific groups of stakeholders have been developed. The messages will evolve throughout the project and will be the backbone of the CDEP and its activities.

- 1) **CS are fundamental for a climate neutral and resilient Europe**
The first message highlights the basic premise of the project. Timely delivery and effective use of climate information is fundamental for a green recovery and a resilient, climate-neutral Europe, in response to climate change and variability. Climate services address this through the provision of climate information for use in decision-making to manage risks and realise opportunities. This message is addressed to institutional stakeholders, Governments and policymakers, citizens, and journalists.
- 2) **Standardisation of CS is key to a cohesive Europe-wide community**
The market and needs for climate information have been developing hugely over the last years and are expected to continue growing in the future. This trend is not reflected in the experience of the existing Climate Services Community, which still lack reciprocal awareness of

interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches. Furthermore, quality assurance (based on standards, best practices or guidance documents) has not been fully developed, although their implementation is needed to ensure climate services' solidity, authoritativeness and legitimacy, as well as to enhance the uptake and scaling up of such services. In this scenario, Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services to all sectors of society. The project will identify the different needs of standardisation of CS, including the ones suggested by the user community, to highlight criteria for certification and labelling, and make CS effective to support climate action.

The collected information will be used to define a taxonomy of climate services, also suggesting community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. A large variety of activities to support the communities involved in European climate services will also be organised. In this framework, the second message is about the importance of standardisation of climate services and the creation of a dedicated taxonomy. The message is addressed to the scientific community, the climate services and the standards community. The benefits of having climate services standards include: building confidence and trust in these services, encouraging providers to improve their quality and offering them alternatives to better align with standard principles, providing a benchmark, supporting equitable access to climate services, and facilitating uptake, among others.

3) Co-production is crucial to increase the uptake of climate services by the community

Along with standardisation, it is fundamental to support the development of an equitable European climate services community. The value of climate services is determined by the level of user engagement, co-design and co-production employed during their development, while resource limitations for any of these aspects constrain their full potential. Co-production of these services together with users is increasingly seen as a necessary good practice approach to provide efficient services that bring together supply and demand. The third message is about the involvement of the whole climate services community (including users and purveyors) in the production and development of services to enhance climate services business innovation. This message is addressed to the scientific community, the climate services community, the business sector, Governments and policymakers and citizens.

4) Trust and engagement are vital in the development of CS

Trust is a key concept in the support and standardisation of climate services. Trust facilitates interactions among people, but also between people and technologies. To support transformative change, climate services must be trustworthy and trusted by all relevant actors. Trust can be gained through a set of shared ethical and technical norms, which implicitly or explicitly define appropriate behaviour by all parties involved and how things should work. Standards are a key element of these norms. To be effective, the development of standards and standardised tools, as well as related validation, verification and certification methods for quality assurance, control and management, needs to identify the expectations of key actors at all scales of governance, including local and regional ones, and their continuous involvement in reaching a community consensus. The fourth message is about creating trust through standards, but also through transparency in the process and continuous engagement of the relevant parties. The message is addressed to the scientific community, the climate services, governments and policymakers, citizens and journalists.

3 Target audiences

Communication and dissemination activities and materials will be crucial to support the Climateurope2 project community engagement (WP6), as well as to reach audiences that are still not using or aware of climate services.

The main target groups for the communication and dissemination activities are identified below:

- **Climate services community** (including those already developing, using or aware of CS) - to inform, provide standards and guidelines, encourage synergies between projects, enhance dialogue and interactions, and build a supportive network.
- **Scientific community** - to share knowledge and expertise across disciplines, promote future research, training on climate services, and to inform about the project research and outcomes.
- **Governments and policymakers** - to improve the understanding of policy/decision-makers on climate services research and relevant activities, including the need for guidelines and standards, and inform evidence-based policies.
- **Standards community** - to foster climate services role in climate resilient standards and ensure the uptake and implementation of standards and guidelines developed in the project.
- **Business sector** - to highlight the benefits of climate services for different economic sectors, increase their uptake and contribute to the expansion of the climate services market.
- **Journalists** - to increase the visibility of climate services and perception as reliable and useful, and to amplify the societal reach of the project.
- **Citizens** - to raise awareness about climate services, inform about their benefits and value, and promote their uptake by society; to provide credible information and encourage a dialogue between science and society.
- **Consortium partners and EC Project Officer** - to ensure effective communication of the project progress.

Figure 1. Climateurope2 target groups

Some of the target audiences are already part of the wider climate services community, in which case the purpose of the activities is to communicate the project outcomes, and foster discussion for reaching consensus and identifying aspects where further research is needed. Other target groups and communities are not familiar with the climate services field, and thus the dissemination and

communication activities aim to raise awareness, encourage and promote the uptake of these services beyond the climate services community.

4 Visual identity

4.1 Visual identity and logo

The visual identity was designed and produced by BSC.

The logo for Climateurope2 features the word "Climateurope2" in a bold, sans-serif font. The letters are filled with a horizontal color gradient that transitions from a deep blue on the left, through light blue and green, to a bright yellow on the right. The "2" is a solid yellow.

Figure 2. The Climateurope2 logo

The description of the logo, the choice of colours, and all the information necessary for the correct application of the logo in its different configurations are included in the visual identity guidelines, a manual for the use of the logo that is available to all partners in the project wiki. The design of the Climateurope2 logo (Fig.2) is based on the lettering of the name of the project that aims to create a modern look for the project, something relatable to the public. Inspired by gradients referring to the graphs used to represent climate data, colour is used as an element to create a vibrant personality for the project. With a colour palette that plays around earth colours without getting too redundant in the ecosystem of projects, it plays along.

Figure 3. Examples of the application of the Climateurope2 logo on different backgrounds

The principal font on the branding is Lato, which can be found on the google-fonts webpage. This ensures the correct display on the web pages and different applications. The accent typography is MADE Kenfolg, a serif typeface that will be used for titles and headers whenever the partners see fit. Once the logo was designed, its applications and **colour palette defined**, the different configurations were produced for application on materials such as slides for oral presentations and posters.

#232120	#0034BE	#ACE2C3
#8E8E8E	#0E76B8	#DDF2BF
#CECECC	#649CC5	#FFF2B1

Figure 4. Climateurope2 visual identity: the colour palette

4.2 Templates

Climateurope2 templates were defined according to the visual identity of the project. Some of the templates, like presentations and posters are produced both for internal and external use, while some templates are for reporting and internal use, e.g. a minutes template, deliverable, milestone and report templates.

The presentation template (Fig.6) will be used for internal meetings and reviews but also for the dissemination and communication of project outcomes to external audiences (scientific community, conferences and workshops, institutional stakeholders, media, general public, etc.)

The Consortium agrees that the language used for communications, hence for the plan, is British English.

Title of the poster

Name of the author(s) and affiliation(s)

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.
- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.
- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.
- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.

Add text or image here

Add text or image here

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101056933. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 5. Climateurope2 visual identity: the poster presentation template

Figure 6. Climateurope2 visual identity: the presentation template – title slide

4.3 Acknowledgements

All communication and dissemination materials produced in the project (posters, presentations, promotional material, publications, etc.) and distributed in physical or electronic format will display the EU emblem and funding text provided below, in line with the EU regulations described in the Grant Agreement:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101056933.

In addition, results disseminated are recommended to include the following disclaimer:

'Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.'

5 Communication and dissemination tools and channels

In order to achieve communication and dissemination actions that effectively meet the project's objectives, Climateurope2 implements the use of various communication channels and tools, including activities, platforms and instruments to reach diverse target audiences in different contexts.

Communication is a comprehensive integration of the various tools and channels used to raise awareness of the project, taking strategic and targeted measures and messages for promoting the project itself and its results to multiple audiences, including the media and the general public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange with all the stakeholders involved. As such, communication is a cross-project task, where the activities included in WP7 collect and drive many inputs coming from different WPs, like WP6 for the involvement of stakeholders, WP5 for the engagement with policy makers and WP4 for the initiatives related to the business sector.

Dissemination, on the other hand, focuses on the disclosure of the results of the project, promoting the circulation of knowledge and outcomes to the ones that can best make use of them. In this way it also enables the value of the results to reach far beyond the original scope.

Both communication and dissemination activities will be targeted to specific audiences with tailored messages and tools.

5.1 Project website

The project website is a digital environment where all public information about Climateurope2 activities will be made available. Since October 2022 (M2), the site has been online, accessible at the URL: <https://climateurope2.eu/> and was developed by BSC. Due to the nature of the Climateurope2 project, which is a Coordination and Support Action, it was important to have an operational website at the early stage of the project. The online presence provides visibility for Climateurope2, gives consistency to the project, provides a place to find all relevant information on activities and provides a space to contact the Climateurope2 team. The website should be understood as a **dynamic and constantly evolving environment**, a space that changes as the project activities grow and is adapted to provide the best visibility for the different activities. In its start-up version, the website is organised into **four sections plus the homepage**. Additional sections will be added later on, when suitable materials are available, including a section on Guidelines and standards as well as a Resources section, divided in the different types of communication and dissemination materials generated by the project. The website will be available for at least 5 years after the end of the project.

Homepage (Fig.7) is designed to highlight the vision and the mission of the project with the latest information and content that shed light on the more relevant activities and outcomes related to Climateurope2. The navigation menu gives access to all sections of the site, while scrolling down the page, one has immediate evidence of the project objectives summarised in three key words: Standardising, Supporting, and Increasing uptake. One section of the homepage is dedicated to highlighting the latest publications regarding events and news. The next section offers space for the participatory platform that will be set up during the course of the project, while the final section is dedicated to a call to join the Climateurope2 network, with a direct link to the registration form. The content of the home page will be enriched with updated and fresh materials that the project wishes to

emphasise as it advances and completes its activities (events, newsletters, deliverables, outcomes, etc.).

Figure 7. Climateurope2 website homepage

About us: the first menu item is dedicated to an in-depth description of the project. The section is divided into 4 subsections:

- **About the project**, with a general description of the project and a reference to the former Climateurope project;
- **Objectives**, a detailed outline of the results the project intends to pursue;
- **Consortium**, where the geographical scope of the project is illustrated with a map and the logos of the partners that are shown with links to their respective sites;
- **Projects and initiatives**, where it is illustrated how the project will establish synergies and make use of knowledge from a large number of previous and current projects, initiatives, networks and international programmes, including relevant sister projects within the Horizon Europe Programme and projects from the Mission on Climate Adaptation.

News and Events: this section is the most dynamic area of the website. This section collects updates on activities and events such as webinars, workshops and conferences. This section is populated as Climateurope2 activities develop during the project; it is intended to keep track of all initiatives related to the project or in which the project is involved. Climateurope2 organises and participates in a number of festivals, webstivals, conferences and other events aimed at the climate services community and wider audiences. On the page dedicated to Events, the users will find more information about the project's upcoming and past events, as well as relevant climate services events organised by other external initiatives. A document with guidelines for publishing news and events on the project website, including criteria and procedures for publication, has been developed by WP7.

Platform: a specific section is dedicated to the Climateurope2 platform. It is a digital environment that aims to ensure that good practices, guidelines, and capacity-building materials are widely available, easy to find, and usable during and after the project's lifetime. The platform also has a community engagement component that allows audiences to reach consensus on the topics tackled by the project.

Contact: this section is dedicated to those who would like to get directly in touch with the project team writing to infoclimateurope2@bsc.es. A form is also available to be filled out to request information.

Finally, the footer, which is present on all pages of the website, contains official and formal information including the EU emblem, the acknowledgement of the funding programme with a disclaimer, the Privacy Policy, Legal Notice, a button to subscribe to the newsletter and links to social media.

5.2 Newsletter

At least 6 electronic newsletters will be issued during the duration of the project to inform and report about Climateurope2's latest activities, including relevant news and outcomes. The newsletter aims to engage the scientific community, institutional stakeholders, media and the general public. The first newsletter will be released in March 2023, and the second in September 2023. The following newsletters are foreseen for September 2024, 2025, and 2026, with a final one which will be released in February 2027 to wrap up the project results. Regarding registration, there will be two options - a static and a dynamic. The static/permanent option will be a slider with a Call-to-Action button on the website homepage, offering viewers the opportunity to register for all Climateurope2 news, updates, and events. The dynamic option will be a pop-up Call-to-Action present on the Climateurope2 website, asking visitors if they wish to register, regardless of the page they land on. This activity is led by LGI.

5.3 Social media

Social media are valuable channels to reach a wider community, raise awareness and increase project visibility, reaching a greater proportion of the target audiences of the project and making the scientific outcomes available in a clear language to the non-specialised public. Social media are also helpful in engaging the scientific community and raising interest regarding the developments of the project, especially among the groups interested in Climateurope2 topics and related stakeholders. A further function of social media is to activate and initiate relationships with potentially interested parties with activities or interests similar to those of Climateurope2. As they polarise interest in the project's topics, social media are the means to start a dialogue with new stakeholders, individuals and organisations being the adequate channel to feed these relationships and keep these audiences informed about the project outcomes.

Climateurope2 has identified three social media channels for the project:

- **Twitter** (Fig. 8)- <https://twitter.com/climateurope2> - with 2000+ followers (inherited from the original account of Climateurope)

Twitter is a platform for rapid communication, consisting of short messages. It requires very direct and clear language for immediate interaction. It is suitable for sharing topics related to the results of the project, news and events or other relevant activities that can be of interest to the community of followers. Twitter is an interactive channel that targets specific audiences with dedicated key messages, thanks to tailored hashtags. The target audiences reached by Twitter include climate services experts, the scientific community, public and private organisations, the media and the general public. A link to the channel is included on the project website homepage.

Twitter activities will use some defined hashtags such as #Climateurope2, #Climateurope2project, #Climateservices, #Ce2fest, #Ce2webst, #Standards4climate, #Climateadaptation, #CE2, #Euproject

- **LinkedIn** (Fig. 9) - a new public project page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/climateurope2/>) with 86 followers, and a private group page (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8573540/>).

LinkedIn is used primarily for professional relations. The public page aims to involve external audiences, while the private group page (from the first Climateurope project) aims to share news, outcomes and information among the partners and selected groups interested in the project activities. A public page was created in order to give more visibility, optimise the SEO (an internet user can't find a private LinkedIn group without being invited into it), and to broaden the project's network and reach, acting as a showcase. The private page acts as an exchange forum, where participants can share information, debate, comment, support research and discuss items easily.

- **YouTube channel** (Fig. 10)- <https://www.youtube.com/@climateurope2609>

YouTube channel (Fig. X) aims to host and collect all recordings of webinars and events organised in the framework of the project along with the videos which will be produced to communicate specific activities, developments and outcomes of the project, as part of the dissemination strategy. The produced content will be organised and divided into playlists allowing better understanding and smoother navigation for viewers. As such, the YouTube

channel targets expert audiences, general public and institutional stakeholders, which might be interested in short videos describing the project's progress.

Data on followers and members of all social media channels refer to February 2023. These accounts are managed and animated by LGI in cooperation with all partners. The Twitter account and LinkedIn group were not born from scratch but take up the activities and network of the Climateurope project with a renewed visual identity and a renewed impetus that is inspired by the new activities that are developed within Climateurope2. KPIs of social media channels are reported monthly.

A **social media planner** (Fig. 11) was developed by LGI. The planner is an internal tool for the project partners to share information about topics, events, news, contents to be covered by the project social media. The planner is a living document that enables the partners to plan the publication of posts on the different channels.

Figure 8. Climateurope2 Twitter account

Figure 9. Climateurope2 LinkedIn account

Figure 10. Climateurope2 Youtube page (video of the first webinar)

Climateurope2

Social Media Planner

OCTOBER 2022													
DATE	TIME	PLATFORM	TYPE	STAGE OF PRODUCTION	GOAL	CAPTION	TEXT	CALL TO ACTION	LINK	HASH/TAGS	TAGS & MENTIONS	COMMENTS	COMMENTATOR
Tuesday 25th	10:45	Twitter	Graphic	Produced	Participation	Save the Date!	Register now for the UK Climate Services Standards and Values Webinar on November 3rd. A great opportunity to learn more about the benefits of #ClimateServices standards.	Registration Link	https://bit.ly/3eVwA2Z	#ClimateServices			
Tuesday 25th	10:45	LinkedIn Page	Graphic	Produced	Participation	Save the Date!	Register now for the UK Climate Services Standards and Values Webinar on November 3rd, presented by Murray Dale, from ICA Consulting. A great opportunity to learn more about the benefits of #ClimateServices standards.	Registration Link	https://bit.ly/3eVwA2Z	#Webinar #ClimateServices			
Tuesday 25th	10:45	LinkedIn Group	Graphic	Produced	Participation	Save the Date!	Register now for the UK Climate Services Standards and Values Webinar on November 3rd, presented by Murray Dale, from ICA Consulting. A great opportunity to learn more about the benefits of #ClimateServices standards.	Registration Link	https://bit.ly/3eVwA2Z	#Webinar #ClimateServices			
							Sign up here: https://bit.ly/3eVwA2Z						
NOVEMBER 2022													
DATE	TIME	PLATFORM	TYPE	STAGE OF PRODUCTION	GOAL	CAPTION	TEXT	CALL TO ACTION	LINK	HASH/TAGS	TAGS & MENTIONS	COMMENTS	COMMENTATOR
Tuesday 1st	10:45	Twitter	Graphic	Produced	Participation	Save the Date!	#ClimateServices standards has evolved through widespread consultation over nearly two years. Curious to learn how? Register now for the UK Climate Services Standards and Values webinar, on November 3rd, to find out!	Registration Link	https://bit.ly/3eVwA2Z	#ClimateServices			
Tuesday 1st	10:45	LinkedIn Page	Graphic	Produced	Participation	Save the Date!	#ClimateServices standards has evolved through widespread consultation over nearly two years. Curious to learn how? Register now for the UK Climate Services Standards and Values webinar, on November 3rd, to find out!	Registration Link	https://bit.ly/3eVwA2Z	#Webinar #ClimateServices			

Figure 11. Climateurope2 social media planner

5.4 Climateurope2 Platform

The Climateurope2 platform will support internal discussions and engage the climate services community by making guidelines, good practices and recommendations regarding climate services widely available, easy to find and usable during and after the project's lifetime. Once developed, the platform will be accessible from the Climateurope2 website. In a secure environment, it will allow the project partners to publish and discuss drafts of guidelines and good practices until consensus is reached and they are ready for public access. For registered users (selected stakeholders) it will provide a space to review the mature drafts and comments. Publicly, it will facilitate access to the final versions of guidelines, good practices and recommendations for climate services via an interactive and user-friendly repository. This is not to be confused with the 'project resource repository' that is for internal use only.

The web application back-end will allow the Climateurope2 members to enter the guidelines and practices document with standardised metadata (title, tags, etc). In the front-end, the applications use that metadata to provide faceted search, automated classification and visualisation services to explore content resources and (using WebLyzard technology) a visual analytics dashboard to oversee the content collection process, assess the quality of the extracted metadata and perform searches that further enrich the application. The platform is aimed at involving specialised audiences and stakeholders, but at the same time it will be one of the project outputs and a collection of materials for wider communication.

The functional and technical requirements are gathered during an iterative stakeholders and project partners consultation, resulting in a high-fidelity prototype of the platform (static-clickable) that will mark the start of the platform development. In periodic sprints using mock-ups, there will be different in-between releases of the platform, before reaching a beta version fully functional by M18. The mock-ups will include feedback on the developments obtained from a panel of experts inside the project. This beta version will facilitate an early interaction of the community with preliminary versions of reports. Working towards the final stable version of the platform in M36, there will again be additional releases in between, but now also feedback will be included from external user groups as well in this later release. The final version will come with a restful Application Programming Interface (API) for future integration in other platforms such as Climate-ADAPT.

The platform will be custom developed using Symfony PHP, including a database for user management behind the platform, a database for metadata best practices and a CMS front-end open to the Deliverable leaders to place their publications. These publications will include the good practices that are extracted from project deliverables by the experts. The practices can include, for example, different parts of a workflow from raw data to a data product. Each good practice publication will follow a metadata template with its own respective DOI/URI, which will be made findable using a repository with a search entry, enabled by using keywords. The visual analytics dashboard (WebLyzard) can be used to measure the impact of publications and good practices. This activity is led by Mariene Informatie Service MARIS BV.

5.5 Press releases

A press release will be prepared for each activity of the project with high public relevance (meetings, events, publications, major outcomes). Press releases will be published on the website and distributed to the media list of all project partners, to reach national and international journalists and get relevant coverage, contributing to raising awareness among the groups interested in the developments of the project. Press releases will be in English and the project partners will provide translation into local languages and publication on their websites. The main target of press releases are journalists, who will in turn contribute to raising awareness of the project among the general public. An internal mailing list with the main communication contact at each partner's institution has been created to facilitate the flow of information regarding press releases. A [Climateurope2 clipping Excel file](#) collecting project appearances in the media and on partners' channels is available on the wiki. This activity is led by CMCC.

5.6 Promotional materials

Promotional materials will be prepared and used to promote the project among the community with a goal to increase its visibility. A digital flyer “Join the Network” (Fig. 12) has already been designed and is available in the registration form to join the CE2 network. It will also be available in the “Resources” section as soon as it is completed.

Also, a roll-up banner will be designed and produced, which will be used for Climateurope2 events or in the context of external events where Climateurope2 is present and has a slot for presentations, sessions, etc. This activity is led by CMCC.

Climateurope2

SUPPORTING AND STANDARDISING CLIMATE SERVICES IN EUROPE AND BEYOND

WHY JOIN THE CLIMATEUROPE2 NETWORK?

Climateurope2 will support the development of future equitable and quality-assured climate services of greater value to society, which will provide trustworthy, user-relevant and usable information.

For that, we need to involve all the actors in the climate services value chain. **We will develop a network across Europe to improve the connection, engagement and promotion of European climate service activities.**

JOIN OUR NETWORK

In our network you will be able to:

- **Engage** with the community of climate services through the interactive Climateurope2 Platform
- **Participate in discussions** on the standardisation of climate services' components with the aim to reach consensus with the different actors involved
- **Have direct access to information** about good practices, recommendations, capacity-building materials, vocabularies and standardisation processes of for climate services
- **Be informed about activities** bringing the network together, including festivals, webstivals, a roadshow, a webinar series, business breakfasts and much more!

 infoclimateurope2@bsc.es

 [@climateurope2](https://twitter.com/climateurope2)

 [/company/climateurope2](https://www.linkedin.com/company/climateurope2)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101056933

climateurope2.eu

Figure 12. Climateurope2 flyer

5.7 Videos

Video is an immediate tool to engage large audiences, inform and educate on project objectives and results. Messages conveyed through video are more engaging and lead to a higher retention rate. Moreover, videos can explain the project's progress in a simple and appealing language, featuring the human face of the project and the community behind it. A variety of video formats will be used to target different audiences through different channels or to tackle various topics related to Climateurope2. All the videos will be collected and displayed on the project's YouTube Channel.

- **Video capsules:** short videos (~1 min) for web and social media use, outlining the aims of the project and its practical applications. The videos will portray the atmosphere of in-person events such as festivals, workshops and roadshows, and will be short excerpts of longer videos. 4 video capsules will be produced. All short videos will have a common style (both in terms of layout and format). These videos are dedicated to the general public, media and stakeholders. The development of short videos is led by the Center for the Promotion of Science (CPN).
- **Longer videos** (~3 min) will summarise the WP outcomes. These videos will showcase some of the project's in-person events (i.e. festivals, roadshows, business breakfasts, events for young researchers, training sessions, etc.) as a starting point/background, combined with interviews with different experts within the consortium. The objectives and the results of the project will be explained by WP leaders in an accessible/non-technical language (with examples and metaphors when suitable), and enriched with the inclusion of animation and infographics. These videos target various groups interested in the development of the project, including scientists, academia, and institutional stakeholders. BSC, LGI and CMCC will contribute to the concept and scripts; LGI will take care of production.

Some of the potential topics are:

- Inclusive standardisation framework for climate services (WP1)
 - Provision of quality assured and fair climate services (WP2)
 - Climate service business innovation and market development (WP3-4)
 - Policy support for climate (WP5)
 - Community engagement for building climate literacy (WP6-7), stressing the development of the CE2 platform
- **Video of art-related activities** in the project to show synergies with non-expert/general public and raise wider curiosity and awareness of the project. This video will be longer, more impactful, and feature some insightful stories around the project, as a short documentary of 10-15 minutes, with different speakers both from the partners and from external collaborations. The production of these videos will be led by CPN.

Other multimedia materials, such as recordings of webinars, webstivals, festivals and other events, will be available on the Youtube channel and on the project website. The website will also host a dedicated page to display the materials of these events (agendas, presentations, pictures, recordings), making them available to academic and research audiences. Other videos may be shot on the occasion of participation in external events. This activity will be led by BSC.

5.8 Podcasts

Podcasts are a popular medium for science communication as they have a flexible format, can reach the international audience, are relatively easy to disseminate, and can be accessed for free by all interested people. Podcast interviews with experts in the network will raise awareness and improve understanding of climate services and relevant concepts. The podcast, being addressed to a large and not specialised audience, should be educational in a smart and light style. LGI is the leading partner of podcast production. The podcasts will be available on the Climateurope2 website, disseminated through the LGI website, as well as published on audio content platforms (i.e. Spotify, Deezer, Soundcloud, ApplePodcasts, GooglePodcasts, etc.). The choice of platforms for the Climateurope2 Podcast will be determined further into the project.

Different podcast formats may be produced, depending on the topic and purpose:

- **Solo speaker** - the podcast will have an educational style, featuring an explanation on one of the main topics/results of the project by an adequate expert. The speaker will be one of the scientists among project partners or from an external party.
- **Interview style** - the podcast will feature a dialogue between an interviewer and an expert, with a journalistic and dissemination approach. The interviewer will be one of the project partners or an external journalist, and the interviewee will be an expert from the consortium.
- **Multiple discussion** - the podcast will be a round table with more people interacting, moderated by an interviewer. The interviewer will be one of the project partners or an external science journalist. The speakers will be different representatives of the project partners as well as representatives from institutional stakeholders.

The standard outline of the podcast, in any of the different formats, will include intro music, some audio clips for transition/introduction of different topics, and outro music. The name of the podcast will be "Climate at your service". The frequency will be defined according to the project's progress, starting with a minimum of 2 podcasts per year. The agenda of topics and questions will be shared and agreed upon with the other project partners.

5.9 Infographics

Visuals are powerful and attractive tools, both in providing scientific insights to the researcher and transmitting science to a wider audience. Collaborations between scientists and graphic designers or other related professionals adept in visual communications offer great potential if these disciplines can come together for mutual benefit. In science, infographics are used to inform, explain, and even entertain. Indeed, infographics will be used to translate complicated messages into easy-to-understand visualisations, boosting reception among diverse audiences. This activity is led by CMCC.

Infographics will be developed for those concepts which require visualisation to digest information from deliverables that provide data and information of interest to multiple audiences and will support dissemination aimed at improving the general public awareness of what a climate service is and how it is delivered, including the different steps of the process to implement climate services.

At least 5 infographics will be produced. The WP7 team, along with the authors of the deliverables, will identify those reports, documents, or policy briefs that will be the source of information for the infographics. The same infographics can be used in multiple communication and dissemination contexts, ranging from the website to social media and newsletters, to videos that will be produced on common topics.

The potential sources of information for infographics include the following:

- Catalogue of Case studies (WP4). One of the objectives of WP4 is to create an inventory of the current market of climate services, including an analysis of its gaps and possible pathways of future developments. This deliverable is a good source for infographics to represent the starting point of the project and the complex scenario of climate services.
- Standardisation of climate services is another key concept for infographics. Once the scenario and mechanism of climate services' delivery are explained, an infographic will outline how Climateurope2 supports the standardisation of climate services and what are the related benefits, for the scientific community, stakeholders/decision-makers and the general public.
- One more topic for infographics will coincide with the Policy brief "pathways for standardisation of CS to climate action", showing practical steps for CS to support policymakers and have tangible impacts on climate action and management.

5.10 Events

The communication and dissemination strategy of the project will include both online and in-person project events, to present and discuss the Climateurope 2 objectives and results. The events will be organised under the umbrella of the activities of WP6 - Community engagement and result also in wider communications opportunities. The events are aimed at building and developing the climate service network across Europe to improve connection, engagement, and promotion of European climate service activities. They will encourage an open exchange of knowledge, expertise, and data, provide a science-user communication interface and improve synergies between regional, national, European and international activities. The objective of community engagement activities is to enhance interaction across the network, mixing traditional communications such as meetings and publications, with innovative, refreshing approaches such as festivals, webstivals and roadshows integrated with social media channels, arts, music and culture.

WP6 includes a task fully dedicated to the organisation of events for the network [M3-50] (CMCC Lead, all WP6 partners). In this task, engagement and support activities and events will be organised to (a) bring the community together (face-to-face and virtually), (b) share knowledge amongst the community, including outputs of the project, and (c) build links across the climate services value chain to enhance the end-to-end interaction.

These activities include the following:

1. Two on-site Festivals (M18, M38) making use of large adaptation events (e.g. ECCA conference) to coordinate the project activities.
2. **Six Webstivals** (M6, M12, M24, M31, M45, M52) to stimulate a lively virtual conversation about multiple climate services domains. Webstivals will be the opportunity to share project guidelines and recommendations through an interactive process of reflection, so as to reinforce the feeling of co-ownership and wider dissemination with network members.

The content for these events can come from the project activities, but also from external sources such as other European-funded projects and organisations. A list of projects and initiatives whose members could be potential participants of the network has been compiled by the consortium and will be used in the future to expand the Climateurope2 network. Registered participants can be involved as speakers or participants in Webstivals later on.

3. A “Roadshow” (M10-M48), a series of smaller events, will be organised in different countries across South East Europe (SEE). Its aim is to promote the Climateurope2 network in the region of SEE, through local stakeholder engagement in their native languages. Ten locations will be selected that were underrepresented in the Climateurope1 network. The project will promote an evolutionary and transformative capacity building about standards and processes in climate services.

Climateurope2 will engage with Copernicus Fora, local stakeholders and knowledge networks to export the outcomes of the project across Europe. Project’s materials will be used to support local actors in the organisation of their own events. By doing so, the project will promote an evolutionary and transformative capacity building about standards and processes in climate services.

4. At least two events (e.g. Business breakfasts) with standardisation, certification or other business stakeholders, organised by DNV AS.

5. At least two events organised by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts discussing the main outcomes of the project relevant to Copernicus Climate Change Services. During the project, WP6 partners and ECMWF will evaluate if these events are organised as a virtual stand-alone event or a session in a face-to-face event.

6. A ‘stakeholders’ perspectives’ webinar series (M13-M54) will promote online discussions ensuring that network participants can share their voices and perspectives on the topics tackled. In addition, further engagement with the climate services and the standards communities will be sought in WP7 through the joint organisation of ‘invited webinars’ with other projects and initiatives.

The scope of each event will adapt to the project's evolution as more advanced outcomes are available to be discussed for feedback. The activities will target the breadth of the climate services community in Europe although they may focus on specific audiences depending on geographic locations, e.g. data-rich and data-scarce environments, coastal/ inland/ mountainous areas, and different sectors in society that will be involved (e.g. urban development, agriculture, energy production, etc.). Over the course of the project the aim is to engage all sectors in need of climate services.

7. Science-meets-policy regional events will specifically target policymakers. Scientists will meet policymakers to brief them on policy-relevant project outcomes. On this occasion, policy briefs produced by the project will be distributed and could be used to initiate a live discussion with the policymakers. These events will be organised under WP5, to deal with local policy and decision concerns from a bottom-up perspective for enhancing climate services uptake. Combining social science research with inter- and trans-disciplinary activities will ensure that WP1-4 efforts are policy-relevant, credible, and suitable for their implementation in the real-world. It will be assessed whether the supply of CS fits the demand and the guidelines on CS standardisation will be developed taking into account the information needs of local target groups, using the regional events as the dedicated forum to collect and share this information. The science-policy events focus on policy-relevant project outcomes (including lessons learnt from Climateurope2, guidelines and best practices on how to make use of them in the local context). They seek to bring together climate scientists and local policymakers and stakeholders (>10 attendees). The participants will be selected in coordination with other WPs in order to address the most appropriate target groups.

In addition to the events organised by the project, Climateurope2 will also target some **major European and International events**, for example conferences or events organised by other projects, to present Climateurope2 results and developments, benefiting from a relevant and expert context and audience. Among these events are the following:

- **NOCCA23**, the 6th Nordic Conference on Climate Change Adaptation, which will be held in Iceland, Reykjavík in April 2023;
- **ECCA Conference** (European Climate Adaptation Conference) which will take place in Dublin in June 2023;
- **NORDIWA**, the Leading Nordic event for water professionals, which will take place in Göteborg in September 2023;
- **CORDEX Conference**, the International Conference on Regional Climate, which will take place in Trieste in September 2023;
- **Adaptation Futures**, the premier international conference devoted entirely to climate change adaptation, which will take place in Canada in October 2023.

Besides the activities listed above, ad hoc dissemination and policy engagement activities will ensure that the agreements, recommendations, and roadmaps resulting from the project are used in the dialogue with the European Commission, to assist the standardisation and promotion of climate services and to provide input to the potential revision of related EU regulations, such as the ESG Taxonomy. Policy-related activities will also attempt to convey the key role that climate services can play in informing and supporting policies and initiatives, such as the EU Climate Change Adaptation Strategy, the Climate Pact or the implementation of the Mission on Climate Change Adaptation and societal transformation.

5.11 Innovative activities

Innovative activities aim to enhance the visibility of climate services, raise awareness, and reach audiences otherwise not aware of this field. The activities target different stakeholder groups.

These activities will target the general public to increase support and awareness of how climate services are part of the EU strategy to tackle climate change. Taking stock of the non-scientific networks of the consortium partners, and building on the legacy of Climateurope, the activities will implement actions that will bring scientific content to non-experts audiences (e.g. science museums, engaging with arts, European Researchers' Night). On the other hand, the activities will target communities that can mediate and amplify the project's reach to society such as journalists and artists. Activities in this task will aim to raise public awareness beyond the CS community, stimulate the circulation of sound and reliable science information through the media, and enhance climate service literacy in the public. Some of the activities will include:

- 1) **activities in collaboration with museums and science centres** such as the European Network of Museums, the Centre de Cultura Contemporània de Barcelona (CCCB), and the Visualization Center C in Sweden and participation in science festivals and ad hoc initiatives, which will help raise awareness beyond the climate services community and reach the general public;

- 2) **two art-science regional calls in Southeast Europe** followed by roadshows in 10 locations directed to raise awareness on the project topics and support an equitable EU community by building capacity in regions with a lower uptake of climate services;
- 3) **dedicated events and activities with journalists' networks** in the framework of journalism festivals and conferences that will enhance the visibility of climate service activities and promote the media uptake of quality-assured and reliable climate services to inform society;
- 4) **participation in initiatives and events at EU level**, such as the European Researchers' Night and the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, fostering public climate services literacy and gender balance. This activity is led by SMHI.

5.12 Clustering activities

Climateurope2 will leverage the collaboration and synergies with relevant EU-funded projects, initiatives, and clusters, such as the HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-03 projects, projects funded by the EC DG RTD and some projects for the implementation of the Mission on Climate Adaptation.

The activities involving sister projects will set up a common framework for similar research initiatives and maximise the communication efforts and opportunities of each of them within the cluster system.

The list of the sister projects of Climateurope2 includes the following:

1. **MAGICA**: Maximising the synergy of European research governance and innovation for climate action, coordinated by Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici, ending in May 2026.
2. **MAIA**: Maximising impact and accessibility of European climate research, coordinated by Basque Center for Climate Change (BC3), ending in May 2025.
3. **I-CHANGE**: Individual change of habits needed for green European transition, coordinated by Centro Internazionale in Monitoraggio Ambientale - Fondazione CIMA, ending in April 2025.
4. **HARMONIA**: Support system for improved resilience and sustainable urban areas, coordinated by Politecnico di Milano, ending in January 2025.
5. **SOCIO-BEE**: Wearables and drones for city socio-environmental observations and behavioural change, coordinated by Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis, ending in November 2024.
6. **COMPAIR**: Compair Community Observation Measurement & Participation in AIR Science, coordinated by Digital Vlaanderen (Digital Flanders), ending in October 2024.
7. **EIFFEL**: Earth Observation applications for climate change adaptation and mitigation, coordinated by the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems, ending in May 2024.

8. PROTECT: Procuring innovative climate change services, coordinated by G.A.C. Group Innovation & Performance for Impact, ending in May 2024.
9. ECFAS: European coastal flood awareness system, coordinated by Istituto Universitario di Studi Superiori di Pavia (IUSS), ended in December 2022.
10. FIRE: Forum for Innovation and Research in European Earth Observation, coordinated by the European Association of Remote Sensing Companies, ended in November 2022.
11. CLIMATEUROPE: European climate observations, modelling and services, coordinated by the UK Met Office, ended in 2021.

5.13 Scientific publications

Public project reports and publications in peer-reviewed journals will disseminate key project findings to the climate services and scientific communities.

Scientific publications based on project methodologies, processes and results will be published as open access, whenever possible (gold open access), or in a self-archiving mode (green open access) on partner websites and research collaboration platforms (when the length of the embargo period is acceptable). Papers will mention in the acknowledgements the Climateurope2 project name, as well as obtained funding from the European Union (EU)/Horizon Europe (including grant number). Journal papers will present the most significant project results at the highest scientific standards and disseminate them to a scientific audience. As they typically involve long time-to-publish periods, these publications will focus on substantial, matured, and empirically verified project results, and are thus more likely to appear towards the project end.

Conference papers will present up to date interim project results of appropriate scientific quality in a timely manner to disseminate them as quickly as possible in the scientific community. This activity is under all partners' responsibility, BSC will collect their contributions.

5.14 Factsheets

A factsheet is a one-page document that provides facts and key points about a topic in a clear, concise, and easy-to-understand way, containing not only text but also charts and images. Factsheets can also be a summary of a longer document. Factsheets are particularly useful to journalists and policymakers, as they help save time by providing key information on a single page.

In Climateurope2, factsheets will be used both for an explanation of key concepts and for summarising relevant documents produced in the project, such as deliverables. The factsheets will be carefully designed, adhering to Climateurope2's visual identity, therefore, clearly recognisable as a Climateurope2 product. They will be shared on the project website and social media, and as promotional material at events organised by or with the presence of Climateurope2.

Possible topics to be covered by the factsheets include, but are not limited to:

- What are climate services?

- Who is working on climate services?
- Why are climate services needed?
- Why are climate services relevant for ... (insurance/health/energy/ agriculture...)?
- Why do we need standards for climate services?
- Other topics might be covered on demand by the consortium or stakeholders.

A minimum of 8 factsheets will be produced in total, to be published every 6 months. This activity is led by the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute SMHI.

5.15 Synthesis reports

Among dissemination activities, synthesis reports are the tool to further distil and integrate materials drawing from project results, written in a non-technical style suitable for policymakers and addressing a broad range of policy-relevant questions. Synthesis reports will be based on executive summaries and synthesis documents from WP1 to summarise and effectively communicate the project outcomes, providing guidance to the climate services and wider scientific community. Deliverable D1.5 refers specifically to the production of the “Final synthesis report with updates on landscape, framework and glossary,” and it’s due by M51. Synthesis reports are a helpful basis for the development of a content for communication and dissemination activities. This activity is led by DNV AS.

5.16 Policy briefs

Climateurope2 dissemination also aims to present project results to selected public, private, and academic institutions through dedicated workshops and policy briefs to support bottom-up EU policies and discuss the potential uptake of the project’s results and the remaining research gaps.

Policy briefs are intended to translate scientific findings into concise documents, enabling the project to reach public administrators and have a potential impact on public policy. Policy briefs will be short (1 to 3 pages), straight to the point and clear to the general public. Through engagement and consultation activities with policymaking groups, a selection of topics will be defined, depending on the issues they are more interested to explore or the ones they are less familiar with. This activity is led by LGI.

5.17 Capacity building

Dissemination activities will also focus on training and capacity building so that the project outcomes and methodologies can be used to educate early-carrer professionals and scientists. Training sessions during project events and online courses for early-career professionals and newcomers to the climate services community will be organised during the project’s lifetime. Input materials (e.g. webinar recordings, presentations) from all these activities will be collected with the support of WPs 1-6, and will be disseminated through the project platform and made available on the YouTube channel. The platform will ensure that all dissemination and capacity-building materials are widely available, easy to

find, and usable during and after the project's lifetime. The platform will also have a community engagement component that allows audiences to interact with each other.

Capacity-building in WP7 will provide exposure and training to scientists and other actors in the climate services community. This interdisciplinary view will unite different communities and open new research opportunities by identifying existing knowledge gaps and potential bridges. In addition, a close connection will be established with JPI-Climate, a like-minded organisation which articulates an important part of European climate research. Synergies with the Copernicus programme will also be built through their participation as a partner in the proposal, while links to the Digital Europe programme (in particular Destination Earth) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) will be ensured through their relationship with some partners (e.g., BSC, CERFACS, ECMWF). The capacity-building activity is led by BSC.

Table 1. Communication/dissemination tools and target audiences

	CS community	Scientific community	Gov. & Policymakers	Standards community	Business sector	Journalists	Citizens	Consortium partners
Website	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Newsletter	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social media	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Press releases						✓		
Videos	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	
Podcasts	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Promotional materials	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Events	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Webinars	✓	✓		✓	✓			✓
Innovative activities	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Clustering activities	✓	✓		✓	✓			✓
Infographics	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Factsheets			✓		✓	✓	✓	
Scientific Publications	✓	✓						
Synthesis reports	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
Capacity building	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
Policy briefs			✓		✓			

6 Monitoring and reporting

An [Excel file](#) has been prepared by the BSC to register all communication and dissemination activities completed by partners during the project execution. All project partners should report their activities regularly. The file is available to all partners on the project wiki and contains the type of activity, a description of the activity, the target audience, date and location, the partners involved, the number of people reached, and information about which WP/Task is associated with the activity. The Excel also contains a sheet for reporting on project publications, indicating the type of publication, authors, title, journal name, volume and pages, status of the publication, and publication identifier.

6.1 Key performance indicators

KPIs have been assigned to a number of communication and dissemination activities planned in the project in order to assess their performance and impact by the end of the project (M54). These are listed in the table below.

Table 2. KPIs

Type of activity	Activity	Target group (s)	KPI/target KPI
C/D/E	Climateurope2 Platform	All	>1000 visits
C	Project website	All	>500 users
C	Social media	All	>3000 total followers
C/D	Press releases	Journalists	>5 press releases
C/D	Videos	All	>500 views
C	Podcasts	All	>100 listeners
C/E	Events	All	>500 total attendees
C/E	Webinar series	CS community, Scientific community	>300 total attendees
C	Innovative activities	All	>200 social media interactions
C	Art-science regional calls	Citizens	>15 applications
C/D	Clustering activities	Scientific community	>10 projects engaged
C	Infographics	All	>100 social media interactions
C	Factsheets	Policymakers, citizens, journalists, business sector	>100 views
D	Scientific publications	CS community, Scientific community	>5 publications
D	Synthesis reports	CS community, Scientific community, Standards community, Business sector	>100 views
C	Newsletter	All	>150 subscribers

D	Capacity building	CS community, scientific community, business	>60 attendees
C/D	Policy briefs	Policymakers	>100 views
C/D/E	Policy event	Policymakers	>10 attendees

7 Exploitation

7.1 Objectives

The **objective** of the exploitation task is to determine a strategy to protect the results developed in the project and ensure their legacy beyond the project's end. As part of the Task 7.5, Exploitation and intellectual property protection and licensing strategies for Project Results developed and owned by consortium partners will be developed. All consortium partners will be participants in the task.

The project will produce a series of tangible results illustrated in Figure 13, which will be available to the climate services community through the Climateurope2 platform (task 7.4). The Exploitation and Innovation Manager (LGI) will monitor the long-term exploitation and sustainability of these key exploitable results, considering intellectual property rights (IPR) and developing exploitation strategies with consortium partners. LGI will support the consortium in the identification of protectable Foreground IP developed during the Project, define exploitation strategies to maximise the Project's impact, and protect the Background IP brought into the Project in order to ensure the quality of exploitation and IPR management. The consortium will adhere to all current EU recommendations in this area and the EU Guidelines for IPR.

7.2 Methodology

Figure 13. illustrates the exploitation roadmap and milestones.

- During the whole task duration, a constant dialogue will be maintained with the project partners, stakeholders identified in WP1 to WP5 and the community (WP6), through the exploitation workshops and the engagement component of the Climateurope2 platform, in order to meet the respective needs, interests and recommendations of the community and stakeholders.
- The two exploitation workshops, which will take place respectively on M12 and M24 are two key milestones of the exploitation task.

- Following the second exploitation workshop, a first version of the exploitation plan will be drafted, considering the outcomes of the two workshops as well as the meetings and the project management board.
- Two exploitation meetings will be held on M36 and M48. Additional exploitation meetings may be organised to discuss the exploitation strategy with selected consortium partners. One exploitation referent will be selected for each organisation of the project consortium to represent their respective organisation's exploitation interests.
- The final exploitation plan D7.5 will be due on M54.

Figure 13. Exploitation roadmap and milestones

The first IP webinar and workshop will be organised in September 2023 (M12). The IP webinar will start by introducing the concepts of Exploitation & IP in the context of Horizon projects. The **Results - Strategies - Beneficiaries (RSB) methodology** (Fig. 14) will be adapted to the context, which will lead to the collection of information from the partners on the background and foreground IP, ownership, goals, risks and initial exploitation strategies. **The outputs of this first workshop will feed into a collaborative IP repository, centralising all IP related information.**

During this first workshop, the implementation of an **Exploitation Help Desk** will be defined. The Exploitation Help Desk will clarify questions and concerns regarding exploitation and IP within project partners, it will be planned depending on partners' needs.

Figure 14. RSB methodology

In September 2024 (M24), the second exploitation workshop will focus on the long-term strategy for exploitation of the Climateurope2 platform: the project resource repository (Task 8.5) and the semantic search tool. This workshop will address their value proposition, governance, business model and legal options among others, with inputs from Tasks 1.3, 3.2 and 4.4. The outputs of this second workshop will be included in the exploitation strategy, enabling potential barriers and drivers for the exploitation plan implementation to be identified and prepared for.

7.3 Key exploitable results and overview of usual routes for exploitation in EU projects

The main technical tools developed by the project will be the Resource repository (task 8.5) and the Climateurope2 platform (task 7.4).

- **The project resource repository** will store all the knowledge and data collected, generated, and processed in Climateurope2. It will be a valuable source of data that can benefit other projects and initiatives willing to use the resources already available or to continue adding new materials to the database, making it a tool that may continue to be used beyond the project's lifetime.
- **The Climateurope2 platform** value proposition, governance, business model and legal options will be assessed in T7.5 to ensure the post-project sustainability of the platform and the legacy of the results emerging from the project. A RESTful Application Programming Interface (API) will be developed to promote the exploitation of the Climateurope2 platform beyond the project's lifetime. A preliminary Business Model Canvas is proposed for the project platform in the proposal and will be completed during dedicated exploitation workshops.

Additional key exploitable results, illustrated in Figure 15, such as capacity building tools, inventories, standardisation processes and good practices and guidelines will be developed during the project.

Figure 15. Summary of the main types of exploitable results to emerge from the project

The possible exploitation routes of the key exploitable results beyond the Climateurope2 project's duration are illustrated in Figure 15.

Figure 16. Possible routes of exploitation

These possible exploitation routes will be updated throughout the project and the final strategies will be reported in the Final Exploitation Plan (D7.5).

8 Internal communication

Management of the internal communication of the project will ensure efficient communication channels between all partners and with the EC to facilitate exchange of key project information, documentation and news, and to facilitate participation in the decision-making process. Internal collaborative tools have been set up, including:

- **Internal project wiki:** repository of information accessible to all partners in the consortium, the External Advisory Board, and interested institutions, gathering useful resources and project documents that are under development.
- **Mailing lists:** a general project mailing list, a scientific mailing list and individual lists to facilitate the communication among participants in the different WPs.
- **Slack channel:** tool for fast interaction among project partners to solve issues, exchange opinions and share documents.
- **Project resource repository:** Content management system to store all the knowledge and data collected, generated and processed in the project.

Project Actors	Results	Data processing level	Communication vectors
General Public & European government bodies	News Public deliverables Future and past events Dissemination material	High	Website and social media
Network	Documents under preparation Inventories (vocabulary, stakeholder mapping, taxonomy) Weblyzard analysis Research information	Medium	Platform
Sister projects			
Interested institutions	Project deliverables and reports Internal meetings Management information Research and technical information	Medium	Wiki
External Advisory Board			
Partners	Footage and source materials (video/audio recording) Qualitative and quantitative research data (interviews, questionnaires, surveys) List of subscribers/participants Network members	Low	Repository
	Practical issues	Low	Slack and mailing list

Figure 17. Project actors, types of information available and internal and external communication vectors